

Size and shape tunability of self-assembled InAs/GaAs nanostructures through the capping rate

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Graphical abstract

InAs/GaAs nanostructure tunability through the capping rate: from quantum rings to completely preserved pyramidal quantum dots.

ABSTRACT: The practical realization of epitaxial quantum dot (QD) nanocrystals led before long to impressive experimental advances in optoelectronic devices, as well as to the emergence of new technological fields. However, the necessary capping process is well-known to hinder a precise control of the QD morphology and therefore of the possible electronic structure required for certain applications. A straightforward approach is shown to tune the structural and optical properties of InAs/GaAs QDs without the need for any capping material different from GaAs or annealing process. The mere adjust of the capping rate allows controlling kinetically the QD dissolution process induced by the surface In-Ga intermixing taking place during overgrowth, determining the final metastable structure. While low capping rates make QDs evolve into more thermodynamically favorable quantum ring structures, increasing capping rates help preserve the QD height and shape, simultaneously improving the luminescence properties. Indeed, a linear relationship between capping rate and QD height is found, resulting in a complete preservation of the original QD geometry for rates above $\sim 2.0 \text{ MLs}^{-1}$. In addition, the inhibition of In diffusion from the QDs top to the areas in between them yields thinner WLs, what could improve the performance of several QD-based optoelectronic devices.

KEYWORDS: molecular beam epitaxy; quantum dot; quantum ring; wetting layer; capping rate; dissolution process.

1. Introduction

Since the experimental realization of semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) and the observation of their unique properties arising from the zero-dimensional confinement, increasing efforts have been made in order to take advantage of such structures for real applications. Epitaxial QDs, and

more in particular InAs QDs, have aroused many expectations not only for the development of more efficient optoelectronic devices, but also as a key element in quantum information applications [1-3]. However, the achievement of small fine-structure splitting energies depends on strict geometrical requirements [4] and further exploration of QD growth conditions may help reduce the dependence on external means to produce entangled photon pairs [5, 6]. Indeed, geometry and composition determine the properties of QDs [7, 8], strongly affecting also the performance of lasers, solar cells or any other optoelectronic devices based on QDs. Most efforts on controlling QD properties have commonly been focused on the growth conditions leading to a good understanding of the QD growth mechanism. The growth rate [9-12] and the growth temperature [13], as well as the time interval between the interruption of the QD growth and the capping process [14] play an essential role in determining the morphology of InAs QDs during their initial formation. Less attention has been paid to the capping process, which is necessary for the implementation of QDs in almost any device application and can significantly affect the final QD properties. Indeed, capping with GaAs entails a heteroepitaxial process which alters the thermodynamic equilibrium structure, leading to a considerable dissolution of QDs and altering their structural properties [15-21]. Fig. 1 (a) shows reported heights of buried InAs QDs, which commonly range within 3-4 nm and whose base is typically near 20 nm width [16, 22-29]. Remarkably, this is observed under standard capping conditions ($\sim 1 \text{ MLs}^{-1}$, 450-530 °C) for very different initial QD heights (QD height before capping), from 4.2 nm up to ~ 10 nm. Therefore, the overgrowth process seems to impose a generalized evolution towards thermodynamic equilibrium whereby QDs are similarly levelled, regardless of the initial QD size. This means that, however accurate the QD growth conditions are, the QD size and shape will ultimately be

affected by the capping process, reducing the QD height to $\sim 3\text{-}4$ nm and limiting to a high extent the tunability of the optical properties.

A minimization of the additional strain introduced in the QD by the capping layer through In-Ga intermixing is generally believed to be behind this dissolution process. Therefore, most efforts aiming to preserve the QDs have been focused on minimizing strain-driven QD dissolution by using strain-reducing layers made of alternative capping materials [24, 29-40]. This means that, unfortunately, even in the event that the strain-field surrounding the QD be sufficiently reduced as to completely preserve the QD, this will occur at the expense of significant and inevitable additional electronic structure modifications. For instance, although the use of GaAsSb capping layers strongly limits the QD dissolution (Fig. 1 (b)), a high Sb content yields a transition of the band alignment into a type-II structure [26]. Likewise, a band alignment transition may also be induced by the introduction of N into the capping layer [28]. The application of other strain-reducing layers such as InGaAs may even lead to a QD shape evolution into columnar QDs [41]. Therefore, strain engineering approaches may give rise not only to a complete modification of the QD band structure, but also to strong structural transitions.

Here we propose a very straightforward way by means of which the metastable state of capped QDs can be controllably tuned farther or closer to the thermodynamic equilibrium state without the need for strain engineering approaches. The simple tune of the capping rate allows us to control the size and, therefore, the optical properties of standard GaAs-capped InAs QDs. Besides, the modified intermixing process also affects the final wetting layer (WL) structure, whose impact on the performance of optoelectronic devices is recently gaining an increasing interest [42-45]. The impact of the capping rate on the properties of InAs/GaAs QDs and WLs are both analyzed in this work.

2. Experimental methods

2.1. Growth details

The samples were grown by solid source molecular beam epitaxy on n^+ (100) GaAs substrates. A series of three samples containing a single QD layer was grown for photoluminescence (PL) studies. In all these samples, 2.8 MLs of InAs were deposited at 450 °C and 0.04 MLs⁻¹ on an intrinsic GaAs buffer layer. The QD layer was subsequently capped by a 30 ML-thick GaAs layer grown at 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 MLs⁻¹ in samples S₀, S₁, and S₂, respectively, followed by a 250 nm-thick GaAs layer grown at 580 °C and 1.0 MLs⁻¹. An additional sample for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and cross-sectional scanning tunneling microscopy (X-STM) measurements, labeled as S₃, was grown containing three QD layers equivalent to those of S₀, S₁, and S₂ (L₀, L₁, and L₂ QD layers, respectively, grown in this sequence), separated from each other by a 50 nm-thick GaAs spacer grown at 580 °C and 1 MLs⁻¹. Finally, a 200 nm-thick GaAs layer was deposited, on top of which a fourth layer of uncapped QDs was grown for reference (L_S).

2.2. Optical and structural characterization

The PL was measured at 15 K using a closed-cycle He cryostat. A He-Ne laser with a power of 3 mW was used as the excitation source and the emitted light was dispersed through a 1 m spectrometer, being detected with a liquid N-cooled Ge detector. The chopped signal was detected with a lock-in amplifier in order to enhance the signal to noise ratio. Cross-sectional TEM measurements were conducted using a JEOL-2100 LaB6 microscope operating at 200 kV. Chemical sensitive dark-field TEM images were taken at the [110] pole axis. Standard tapping mode atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements with antimony-doped Si tips were also

used to characterize surface QDs.. X-STM measurements were performed at liquid nitrogen temperature (77 K) on a (110) surface plane of the sample, which was obtained by cleavage in situ under ultra-high vacuum conditions ($p < 4 \cdot 10^{-11}$ Torr). Polycrystalline tungsten tips prepared by electrochemical etching were used for X-STM measurements. The filled state topography images were obtained in constant current mode (50 pA) at high negative voltages (-3V), strongly suppressing the electronic contrast, so that mainly topographic information is drawn through this imaging mode [46]. Current image mode, recording the tunnel current during surface scanning, was additionally used for more accurate determination of nanostructure shape.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. PL characterization

The impact of the capping rate on the optical properties was analyzed in three different QD layers in which the QDs were capped at 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 MLs⁻¹ (samples S₀, S₁, and S₂, respectively). Three layers equivalent to those of samples S₀, S₁, and S₂ (layers L₀, L₁, and L₂, respectively) were also grown in a multi-QD-layer sample (S₃). Fig. 2 (a) shows the 15 K PL spectra of samples S₀, S₁, and S₂, together with the spectrum obtained from the sample containing the equivalent QD layers (S₃). A redshift of the PL peak energy is found with an increase of the capping rate: from 1181 eV, capping at 0.5 MLs⁻¹ (S₀), to 1118 eV, capping at 1.0 MLs⁻¹ (S₁), and to 1096 eV, capping at 2 MLs⁻¹ (S₂). Three peaks at similar energies are also observed in the PL from the multi-QD-layer sample (S₃), corresponding to the emission from the three QD layers equivalent to those of S₀, S₁, and S₂. The very good match between the PL peaks in the different samples confirms the reproducibility of the results. The shift of the PL peak to lower energies is indicative of a QD morphology evolution when the capping rate is increased. In addition to the

redshift of the PL peak energy, improved linewidth and integrated intensity are achieved with a high capping rate (Fig. 2 (b)). The full width at half maximum (FWHM) is reduced from 61 to 42 meV when the capping rate is increased from 0.5 (S_0) to 2 MLs^{-1} (S_2), whereas the integrated intensity is almost doubled.

3.2. TEM characterization

Statistical results on the QD size and shape can be drawn from TEM measurements. Fig. 3 (a) shows g002 dark-field TEM images taken on the [110] pole axis containing views of the layers L_0 , L_1 , and L_2 in sample S_3 , along with a high-resolution view of the surface QD layer, L_S . A number of more than 60 QDs from each layer was measured, finding no significant difference for the base diameter, which is within the range of 21.0 ± 0.5 nm in all the samples. As for the QD height distribution, represented in Fig. 3 (b), average values of 3.72 ± 0.14 , 3.96 ± 0.16 , and 4.41 ± 0.22 nm, were found for the L_0 , L_1 , and L_2 layers, respectively, while the height of the surface unburied QDs was found to be 4.38 ± 0.22 nm, closely matching that of L_2 . A change in the QD height is therefore confirmed to be the main factor affecting the PL properties. A complete preservation of the QD height and size dispersion is achieved capping at 2 MLs^{-1} , while lower capping rates lead to a reduction of the QD height and its dispersion by means of a QD shape evolution from a full pyramidal shape to a truncated or lens-shaped QD. Hence, high capping rates preserve not only the QD height but also its geometry, yielding highly strained QDs far from the thermodynamic equilibrium.

For the used capping temperature, it can be assumed that bulk migration is minimal, so that the strong dependence of the QD size and shape on the capping rate must be governed by slow surface In-Ga intermixing processes with characteristic times in the range of ~ 1 s at such a capping temperature. This would explain the typical QD heights reported under standard

overgrowth conditions, whereby such capping rates are low enough to favor a thermodynamically controlled regime, leading to a strong initial dissolution of the pyramidal QD apex [47, 48]. Contrarily, an increase of the capping rate will kinetically restrain surface intermixing, facilitating the preservation of metastable QD structures and significantly increasing the aspect ratio. Overgrowth kinetics was already used to tune the electronic structure of QDs through growth interruptions [49]. Moreover, the capping rate itself was suggested to influence In-Ga intermixing and, therefore, QD dissolution [20], and was found to affect the geometry of partially covered QDs [21]. Indeed, the growth rate of GaAsSb(N) capping layers has recently been proven to affect the QD decomposition process [40,50]. Our results demonstrate that the final metastable QD structure can therefore be tuned by simply adjusting the capping rate, enabling the achievement of highly strained QDs far from the thermodynamic equilibrium and breaking the generalized trend observed under standard capping conditions. Remarkably, this is achieved even in a system with a high lattice mismatch between InAs QDs and GaAs capping layer ($\Delta a \sim 7\%$) without the use of strain-engineering strategies [39].

3.3. Structural and optical properties correlation

As observed in Fig. 4 (a), the height of capped QDs follows a linear dependence on the capping rate and their complete preservation is achieved at capping rates as of $\sim 2.0 \text{ MLs}^{-1}$. The higher preservation of the QD height at faster capping rates leads to a redshift of the PL peak energy. Moreover, the PL peak energy follows the expected trend as a function of the average QD height in each layer (Fig. 4(b)) [51]. Besides the strong impact on the ground state transition energy, more localized electron and hole wavefunctions in k space are expected for higher QD height, resulting in an enhanced ground state optical matrix element in the measured range and independently of the QD shape [52]. This factor along with a stronger carrier confinement [53]

are in agreement with the enhanced PL integrated intensity with the QD height. On the other side, the TEM measurements show that the size dispersion observed in the uncovered QDs is preserved for QDs capped at a high growth rate, while it narrows down when lower capping rates are used (see Fig. 3 (b)). This is, in principle, in disagreement with the PL FWHM evolution observed in Fig. 2 (b), since a broader QD size distribution is intuitively expected to yield a broader PL linewidth. Nevertheless, a narrower dispersion of the effective bandgap is found in Fig. 4 (b) for the higher QDs (capped at higher growth rates), despite the higher size fluctuations within the ensemble. This is a consequence of the stronger dependence of the effective bandgap energy on the QD height for smaller QDs. Hence, this factor seems to be governing the PL emission shape counterbalancing the broader QD size distribution and giving rise to the narrower emission linewidth for the QD layers capped at higher rates.

3.4. X-STM characterization: effect on the wetting layer

For further understanding on the impact of the capping rate, sample S₃ was analyzed by X-STM. In this technique, the cleaved surface is atomically resolved providing additional information on the QDs as well as on the WL. Fig. 5 shows representative topography images of the nanostructures found in L₂, L₁, and L₀ (Fig. 5 (c), (d), and (e), respectively). The bright horizontal lines are the top zig-zag rows of the cleaved surface corresponding to atomic planes, which are separated by one atomic bilayer and define the resolution along the growth direction in our measurements (0.56 nm). Indium atoms in the group-V sublattice give rise to brighter spots. The pyramidal shape is distinguished in the highest QDs from L₂ (capped at 2MLs⁻¹) showing well-defined lateral facets (Fig. 5 (a)). This shape is not observed in L₁ and L₀ QD layers (Fig. 5 (b) and (c)), where the QD apex dissolves and the system evolves into lens-shaped QDs [50]. Some crater-like structures were also found in layer L₀ (capped at 0.5MLs⁻¹) (Fig. 5 (d)), which

represent the first stage in the evolution of the QDs into quantum rings (QRs) (Fig. 5 (e)) [15, 54, 55]. The typical QR shape is perfectly identified on the current image in Fig. 5 (f), showing the outline of the nanostructure cross-section typically found in QRs [55]. InAs QRs are commonly fabricated starting from partially covered InAs QDs and applying a brief post-growth annealing (<1 min) [15]. Annealing at 470 °C, the temperature used for capping QDs in our sample, has been found to be sufficient to obtain well defined QRs [56]. The capping rate at this QD layer is so low (~8 nm/min) that the outward migration of In atoms from the lens-shaped QD center region becomes a relevant process, giving rise to the formation of some QR structures without the need of growth interruptions. This indicates that the QR morphology is closer to the thermodynamic equilibrium. The structure evolution is kinetically controlled during the overgrowth, so that adjusting the capping rate allows tuning the final metastable structure, from completely preserved pyramidal QDs, to partially dissolved lens-shaped QDs, to QRs. This morphological evolution is likely driven towards a homogeneous quantum well structure as the thermodynamic equilibrium state [16, 47].

The WL in each QD layer was also analyzed by X-STM. Fig. 6 shows representative topography images of the WL in L₀, L₁, and L₂ (Fig. 6 (a), (b), and (c), respectively). The topographic contrast is induced by the outward relaxation of the cleaved surface due to the compressive strain stemming from the WL. Our analyses are performed over an extended region along the WLs, covering a total length between 200 and 400 nm for each WL. The considered areas are chosen to be sufficiently distant from any QD in order to exclude their effects on the WL in the neighborhood of the QD. The results clearly show a reduction of the WL thickness with the capping rate. In order to quantitatively assess the differences between the WLs, the outward relaxation profile of each layer was averaged over the whole imaged area and this averaged

profile is depicted in Fig. 6 (d). The comparison between the areas under the outward relaxation profiles (i.e. the integral of the contrast profiles) provides a direct information on the difference in the amount of In present in each WL [56, 57]. The average areas under the profiles, normalized with respect to the area under the L_0 profile, are depicted in the inset of Fig. 6 (d). A reduction of 37% in the outward relaxation area is found when the capping rate is increased from 0.5 to 2 MLs^{-1} , pointing out the significant reduction in the content of In in the WL. This difference can be understood as another result of the decreased dissolution of the QDs when a high capping rate is used: for low capping rates the strain can be relieved through the flattening of the QD pyramidal shape, which leads to an In segregation from the QD back to the WL in an evolution towards the thermodynamic equilibrium state [16, 47]. Contrarily, when the capping rate is high, this process is suppressed by a kinetic effect, and the In concentration outside the QDs will remain lower. The occurrence of this dissolution process during capping is also forecast by kinetic Monte-Carlo simulations, which predict that In atoms redistribute from the QD tops to the areas in-between them [36]. Hence, capping at high rates not only allows the preservation of the QD height, but also reduces, to a large extent, the WL thickness by the inhibition of In atoms redistribution. Therefore, this approach provides an additional degree of freedom to improve carrier transport in QD photodetectors [43] and solar cells [45] or to reduce the open-circuit voltage drop induced by the WL [42, 44] among other possible benefits.

3.5. Application of the high-growth-rate approach to large QDs

In order to further assess the effectiveness of high capping rates in the preservation of QDs of different sizes, a new sample was grown, in which the QD growth conditions were intentionally modified in order to achieve a broader height distribution containing also QDs significantly larger than those analyzed above. To do that, a single buried QD layer was grown, on an intrinsic GaAs

buffer layer, depositing 2.8 MLs and setting the growth temperature at a higher value, 490 °C, leading to longer diffusion lengths of the adatoms [13]. The QD layer was subsequently capped by a 30 ML-thick GaAs layer grown at 2 MLs⁻¹, followed by a 200 nm-thick GaAs layer grown at 580 °C and 1.0 MLs⁻¹. A surface QD layer was subsequently grown on top at the same growth conditions for comparison.

The height of a set of QDs from both surface and buried layers was measured by AFM and TEM, respectively (although the surface layer was also analyzed by TEM, the number of QDs analyzed in this case could not be high enough to allow a reliable comparison of such a broad and complex height distribution). As observed in Fig. 7 (a), the new growth conditions led to a broader QD height distribution in the uncapped layer, ranging between ~4 to ~12 nm. In addition, the broad population fits to a trimodal distribution with mean values of 5.0 ± 0.2 , 7.3 ± 0.2 , and 10.7 ± 0.3 nm. The inset shows an AFM phase image in which a QD of each family is labelled as 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Remarkably, the overgrowth at 2 MLs⁻¹ of the buried QD layer led in this case to the preservation of the QDs in all the range of heights (Fig. 7 (b)). Indeed, a trimodal QD distribution was also found in this layer with mean values very close to those in the surface layer: 4.5 ± 0.2 , 7.0 ± 0.2 , and 10.5 ± 0.6 nm. The inset shows a TEM image with a QD of each of the three families, labelled as 1, 2 and 3, respectively. This means that the high-capping-rate approach is not restricted to small height QDs and can also be applied to preserve significantly large QDs, avoiding the decomposition of QDs with heights in the range between ~4 to ~12 nm. This provides a new way of achieving buried InAs/GaAs QDs with a large height.

1. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have shown a very straightforward approach to tune the structural, and therefore the optical properties, of InAs QDs capped with GaAs through the capping rate, without the need for alternative strategies. The QD dissolution process induced by strain-driven In-Ga intermixing is kinetically controlled during overgrowth, so that the final metastable structure is ultimately determined by the capping rate. While low capping rates lead to the evolution of QDs into more thermodynamically favorable QR structures, increasing capping rates help preserve the QD height and shape, simultaneously improving the luminescence properties and leading to its complete preservation for rates above $\sim 2.0 \text{ MLs}^{-1}$, independently of the initial QD height. In addition, the inhibition of In diffusion from the QDs tops to the areas in between them yields thinner WLs. This is a potentially beneficial achievement for the development of more efficient optoelectronic devices directly influenced by the presence of the WL, such as QD infrared photodetectors or QD solar cells. Most probably, this simple approach could be transferred to other QD structures based on different materials, taking advantage of an easy way to control the final QD metastable structure.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. (a) Average height of InAs/GaAs QDs reported by different authors before (when available) and after the capping process (red and blue dots, respectively). A schematic of the QD dissolution process during capping is also represented in the inset, whereby the QD top flattens

through surface In-Ga intermixing and surface diffusion of In leads to the WL thickening (orange layer). (b) The upper image shows a completely preserved QD, achieved by the application of a GaAsSb capping layer (from ref. 25). This QD is therefore identical to the uncapped ones. A typical QD capped with GaAs is shown on the lower image (from ref. 26), where a flatter QD top and thicker WL are observed.

Figure 2. 15 K PL spectra of samples S_0 , S_1 , S_2 , and S_3 . The very good match between the PL peaks in the different samples confirms the reproducibility of the results. The apparent shoulder at ~ 1.2 eV suggesting the presence of a fourth peak at higher energies is only due to a drop in the system responsivity, which also gives rise to a notch-like shape in the PL curve of S_0 . The inset shows the integrated intensity and FWHM as a function of the capping rate. Lines are guide to the eye.

Figure 3. (a) g200 dark-field TEM images of representative areas of L_0 , L_1 , and L_2 in sample S_3 , along with a high-resolution view of the surface QD layer, L_S . (b) QD height distributions measured by TEM for layers L_0 , L_1 , L_2 and L_S plotted in a box chart, together with the corresponding histograms. The box is defined by the 25th and 75th percentiles, where the horizontal line and the solid square in the center of the box are the median and the man of each population, respectively. The lines extending vertically from the boxes (whiskers) are determined by the 5th and 95th percentiles.

Figure 4. (a) QD height as a function of the capping rate in the three different layers studied by TEM. The black dashed line represents the uncapped QD height, indicating a completely suppressed decomposition process. The blue dashed line is a linear fit to the QD heights at L_0 , L_1 , and L_2 . The two different background colors indicate two different regimes, whereby the QD height is first linearly increased with the capping rate and then completely preserved for capping

rates above $\sim 2 \text{ MLs}^{-1}$. (b) 15K PL peak energy as a function of the QD height showing the stronger dependence on dispersion for smaller QD heights.

Figure 5. X-STM topography image of the nanostructures found at L_2 (a), L_1 (b), and L_0 (c-e), showing the evolution of QDs into QRs for low capping rates. (f) Current image mode of (e), showing the outline of the nanostructure typically found in QRs.

Figure 6. Representative X-STM topography images of the WL at L_0 (a), L_1 (b), and L_2 (c). (d) Relaxation profiles of the WLs averaged along the overall measured WL length at L_0 , L_1 , and L_2 . The inset shows the average relaxation area as a function of the capping rate, normalized to that of L_0 (lowest capping rate). The blue line is a guide to the eye.

Figure 7. (a) Surface QD height distribution measured by AFM, together with the fit to a normal distribution with three peaks. Three different size populations are observed and labelled as 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The inset shows a phase AFM image showing QDs within the three populations. The QDs labelled as 1, 2 and 3 have a height of 4.0, 7.5 and 11.0 nm, respectively. (b) Height distribution measured by TEM of the QDs covered at 2 ML/s , together with the fit to a normal distribution with three peaks. The same three size populations than in the uncapped QDs are observed. The inset shows the composition of two TEM images showing a QD of each family, with heights of 4.5 nm (QD 1), 6.9 nm (QD 2) and 9.3 nm (QD 3).